

experiment was carried out in the Jayakwadi Command Area during kharif (Jul-Nov) 1984 at MAU. The dominant weeds were *Acalypha indica*, *Dinebra retroflexa*, *Corchorus aestuans*, *Digera arvensis*, *Cynodon dactylon*, *Alysicarpus rugosus*, *Abutilon indicum*, and *Cyperus rotundus*.

Maximum grain yield (2.2 t/ha) was recorded with pendimethalin at 0.75 kg ai/ha supplemented with one hand

weeding at 6 wk after sowing (WAS). Grain yield was significantly superior to those with one hand weeding at 6 WAS and butachlor and thiobencarb application at 1.50 kg ai/ha. One hand weeding at 6 WAS, and applying butachlor and thiobencarb each at 1.50 kg ai/ha proved ineffective in controlling weeds in upland irrigated rice. Among the herbicides, pendimethalin was the most effective in

increasing grain yield, followed by oxadiazon (see table).

Economic analysis indicates that weeding and hoeing done twice at 3 and 6 WAS gave the highest profit. The price of pendimethalin is not available, but yields were higher than with the recommended cultural practice. When labor is short, preemergence application of pendimethalin at 1 kg ai/ha can be done, provided it is economical. *J*

Pest Control and Management

OTHER PESTS

A new virulent strain of rice root-knot nematode from Agartala, India

S. C. Sahu, Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack 753006, Orissa, India; and M. L. Cha wla, Indian Agricultural Research Institute, New Delhi 110012, India

Root-knot nematodes are considered severe pests of upland rice. We surveyed rice nematodes in eastern India and found rice plants heavily infested with *Meloidogyne graminicola* in Agartala. These showed bigger galls on roots compared to those produced in Cuttack and Kerala. To know whether the Agartala population is different from the Cuttack and Kerala populations, a pot experiment was carried out. The three populations were inoculated into 5 rice varieties planted in 200 ml sterilized soil at 200 larvae/pot. Egg mass counts were taken after the first generation (21 d after inoculation) and compared (see table). The Agartala isolate reproduced equally well in all the five varieties while

Rice root-nematode egg masses (transformed values) 21 d after inoculation, India.

Variety	Egg masses (no.) from		
	Cuttack	Agartala	Kerala
Annapurna	4.88	4.05	6.52
Parijat	4.95	6.57	4.13
IR36	2.40	4.97	2.36
MW10	1.47	3.33	1.39
CR190	2.37	4.54	2.09
CD at 5%	1.20	ns	1.06
at 1%	1.71	ns	1.50

the two other isolates differed significantly in their reproduction. CR190, MW10, and IR36 were rated resistant to Cuttack and Kerala isolates while Annapurna and Parijat were susceptible. The Agartala isolate is considered as a new biotype for all the five varieties found susceptible to it. *J*

Plant nematodes in rice fields

S. Ramakrishnan and G. Varadharajan, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University Nematology Laboratory, Kancheepuram, India

We surveyed 3 districts in Tamil Nadu, India (South Arcot, North Arcot, and Chingleput), for the occurrence of rice phytonema. We covered a total of 110 blocks: 28 in Chingleput, and 36 in each of the 2 other districts. The reported genera in the rice rhizosphere were *Hirschmanniella*, *Tylenchorhynchus*, *Helicotylenchus*, *Criconemoides*, and *Hoplolaimus* spp. Their relative proportion in the soil and roots are

Proportion of different nematode genera in the soil and mts of rice.

Genus	Proportion in soil (%)	Proportion in roots (%)
<i>Hirschmanniella</i>	72.2	93.3
<i>Tylenchorhynchus</i>	17.9	5.4
<i>Helicotylenchus</i>	7.2	1.3
<i>Criconemoides</i>	2.0	—
<i>Hoplolaimus</i>	0.7	—

given in the table.

The predominant nematode is *Hirschmanniella* sp. which is found in both soil and roots. *Criconemoides* and *Hoplolaimus* spp. were not recovered from the roots. They occur in small proportion and were not economically important. *J*

Efficacy of nets to prevent bird damage to rice

J.M. Crisostomo, D.B. Estaño, and B.M. Shepard, Entomology Department, IRRI, and J. Olvida, National Crop Protection Center, College, Laguna, Philippines

Nylon nets were placed over three rice varieties to determine their effectiveness against bird damage during the 1985 dry season.

Bird damage percentage in traditional varieties. Masapang, Victoria, Philippines, 1985 DS. * = significant difference between treatments 1 P = 0.05.